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Refine Bio-Savar-Laplace law

Annotation

It is indicated that the Biot-Savart-Laplace law is not derived from Maxwell's equations, but is the result of solving Maxwell's equations for a wire with direct current. It is shown that a direct current wire creates in its vicinity a magnetic induction vector, the cylindrical projections of which are determined in a form close to the original formula. It is shown, in addition, that along with the magnetic flux, a flux of electromagnetic energy propagates, which is part of the power of the current source. It is shown that the vector potential has no formal connection with Maxwell's equations and its application in physics is devoid of substantiation by such a connection.

As a result, it is shown that the existence of a vector potential contradicts the law of conservation of energy.

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1. Introduction

The Bio-Savart-Laplace (BSL) law was obtained experimentally and its formula has a well-known form:

$$\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{c} \int \frac{[\mathbf{j}(\mathbf{r}'), (\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}')]_d}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|^3} d^3\mathbf{r}'. \quad (1)$$

It is generally accepted that *"this law is a consequence of two Maxwell's equations for the magnetic field, provided that the electric field is constant"* [1]. The

conclusion is as follows. A vector potential is introduced that satisfies the equation

$$\mathbf{H} = \text{rot}(\mathbf{A}), \quad (2)$$

and the gauge invariance condition

$$\text{div}(\mathbf{A}) = 0. \quad (3)$$

Путем преобразования этих уравнений выводится закон БСЛ в виде уравнения (1). Этот закон устанавливает зависимость магнитной напряженности от постоянного тока проводимости. Известно также уравнение Максвелла, связывающее магнитную напряженность с постоянным током проводимости, а именно

$$\text{rot}(\mathbf{H}) = \mathbf{J}. \quad (4)$$

By transforming these equations, the BSL law is derived in the form of equation (1). This law establishes the dependence of the magnetic strength on the direct current of conduction. Also known is the Maxwell equation, which relates the magnetic strength to the constant conduction current, namely

1. If we agree that all phenomena in the field of electrodynamics are described by Maxwell's equations, then we must admit that equation (1) is not rigorous and requires refine. But this in no way diminishes the merits of the authors of this law, who were able to discover and formulate it from scratch, when there was nowhere to wait for clues. The proposed article is devoted to refine this law.

2. The vector potential has no formal connection with Maxwell's equations. We also note that the condition of gauge invariance can be met in many ways, which introduces arbitrariness in physics, which contradicts the very spirit of classical physics. At the same time, the application of this condition in the indicated proof serves as a justification for the further use of the vector potential in other areas of physics [2]. But since the vector potential has no formal connection with Maxwell's equations, its application is devoid of this justification.

Further, it will be shown that, at least for a long wire, the vector potential can be dispensed with and the solution is complete, confirmed experimentally, but more complicated than in the existing BSL.

2. Mathematical model

It was shown in [3] that Maxwell's equations for a DC wire have the form

$$\text{rot}(\mathbf{J}) = 0, \quad (a)$$

$$\text{rot}(\mathbf{H}) - \mathbf{J} - \mathbf{J}_o = 0, \quad (b)$$

$$\operatorname{div}(J) = 0, \quad (c)$$

$$\operatorname{div}(H) = 0. \quad (d)$$

where H, J are magnetic strengths and current densities. We will use cylindrical coordinates r, ϕ, z and consider

- the main current density of the oz axis J_o ,
- density of additional currents J_r, J_ϕ, J_z ,
- magnetic strengths H_r, H_ϕ, H_z are radial, circumferential and longitudinal, respectively.

It is important to note that the full system of Maxwell equations is used, and not the abbreviated system of two equations (b, d), which is considered acceptable for magnetostatics. Such a short system does not provide a solution even for a DC wire. In contrast, a complete system of equations allows you to find a solution for the flow of energy **inside** (rather than outside) the wire.

In [3], the solution of Maxwell's equations for a direct current wire is considered in detail and it is proved that the solution exists only for nonzero additional currents J_r, J_ϕ, J_z . The solution has the following form:

$$J_r = j_r(r) \cos(\alpha\phi + \chi z), \quad (12)$$

$$J_\phi = j_\phi(r) \sin(\alpha\phi + \chi z), \quad (13)$$

$$J_z = j_z(r) \sin(\alpha\phi + \chi z), \quad (14)$$

$$H_r = h_r(r) \cos(\alpha\phi + \chi z), \quad (15)$$

$$H_\phi = h_\phi(r) \sin(\alpha\phi + \chi z), \quad (16)$$

$$H_z = h_z(r) \sin(\alpha\phi + \chi z), \quad (17)$$

where

$j(r), h(r)$ are some functions of the r coordinate,

α, χ are some constants.

In [3] it was proved that in a direct current wire the trajectory of a point with a constant current density and constant magnetic strengths on a cylinder of constant radius is a helix. In addition, many trajectories pass through each circle, on which the strengths and current densities change sinusoidally depending on ϕ . Hence,

the line on the cylinder of constant radius, along which the point moves so that all strengths and current densities remain constant, is a helical line.

For example, in Fig. 1 shows three helical lines described by stream functions: a thick line at $\alpha = 2, \chi = 0.8$, a middle line at $\alpha = 0.5, \chi = 2$, and a thin line at $\alpha = 2, \chi = 1.6$.

Further, it will be shown that **outside** the wire (where there is no current), the line with constant magnetic intensity on a cylinder of constant radius is a helical line.

The very fact of the existence of a magnetic field with a spiral configuration around a conductor with a constant current was established by Oersted in 1820 [127, p. 184]. In fig. 2 shows a photograph of a wire soaked in magnetic fluid (magnified 20 times). The spiral lines formed by the magnetic fluid are visible. This photograph indicates the existence of spiral lines of magnetic strengths.

Fig. 2.

3. Strengths in the vicinity of the wire

The solution obtained in [3] makes it possible to find the magnetic field created by the current **outside** the wire. To do this, it is enough to take the solution at $r > R$, where R is the radius of the wire. In this case,

we find that the magnetic strengths outside the wire are determined by the following formulas:

$$h_z''(r) + h_z'(r) - h_z(r) \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{r^2} + 1 \right) = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$h_\varphi(r) = -\frac{\alpha}{\chi} \frac{h_z(r)}{r}, \tag{2}$$

$$h_r(r) = \frac{-1}{\chi} h_z'(r). \tag{3}$$

With the known function $h_z(r)$, functions (2, 3) can be found. The solution to equation (1) is the modified Bessel function. In fig. 3 shows the functions (1, 2, 3) for

$$\alpha = 0.25, \chi = 0.5, R = 0.002, r > R. \tag{4}$$

In accordance with the BSL law, the function of the circumferential magnetic intensity of an infinitely long wire has the form:

$$h_{BSL}(r) = \frac{J_o}{4\pi r}. \tag{5}$$

This formula, as a special case of the BSL law, has been repeatedly tested experimentally and there is no doubt about it. But our task is to **refine the BSL law** so that it becomes a real consequence of Maxwell's equations.

Fig. 3 (BioSavarLaplas.m)

In the second window in Fig. 3 the dotted line shows a function of the form

$$h_{\varphi 2}(r) = \frac{R h_\varphi(R)}{r}. \tag{6}$$

This example shows that function (6) is a good approximation of function (2), i.e.

$$h_{\varphi 2}(r) \approx h_{BSL}(r). \quad (7)$$

Thus, an analytical relationship was obtained between the strength $h_{BSL}(r)$, perpendicular to the wire and determined by the BSL law for an infinitely long wire, and the result $h_{\varphi 2}(r)$ of solving Maxwell's equations for a wire with direct current.

The BSL law establishes that there are no other projections of the strengths created by the current in the wire, except for $h_{BSL}(r)$. In order for the BSL law to be completely a consequence of Maxwell's equations, it must be assumed that there are still strengths directed along the radius of the wire $h_r(r)$ and along the axis $h_z(r)$ of the wire. So, the refined BSL law is that

a wire with direct current creates a vector of magnetic strength in the vicinity of the wire, the cylindrical projections of which are determined by (1, 2, 3)

All these strengths are created by current in a section perpendicular to the radius r . Thus, the strengths of an infinitely long wire have the form (2.15, 2.16, 2.17), where the values $h(r)$ included in these formulas are determined by (1-3).

In fig. 4 shows the hodograph of the strength vector

$$\vec{H}_{zf} = \vec{H}_z + \vec{H}_f, \quad (8)$$

where the terms vectors are defined by (2.12, 2.13) for fixed values of the coordinates r, φ . The hodograph is constructed under conditions (4) and

$$r = 0.0026, \quad \varphi = 0, \quad h_{\varphi}(r) = -2000, \quad h_z(r) = 11. \quad (9)$$

A point with certain vectors values $\vec{H}_z, \vec{H}_f$ is highlighted on the wire. Their sum $\vec{H}_{zf}$ is indicated by a point on the hodograph. It should be noted that the modulus of the vector $\vec{H}_z$ is much less than the modulus of the vector $\vec{H}_f$ - see also Fig. 3. This was the reason that the authors of the BSL law did not notice this projection of strength. The values of the projections H_f and H_r coincide in order of magnitude. Apparently in those ancient times it was difficult to determine the direction of the magnetic induction vector. Nowadays, H_r can be found experimentally.

Fig. 4.

3. Energy flow

Consider the energetics of the interaction of current in a wire with magnetically sensitive elements. This interaction requires energy consumption from the current source. The appearance of a ferrite part (for example) in the vicinity of the wire causes an increase in current and the corresponding additional energy is spent on moving this part. This energy can only be transferred to the part by the energy flow. Therefore, in addition to the magnetic field, a flow of electromagnetic energy must act on the part.

In [3] it is shown that in the vicinity of the wire, in addition to the magnetic strength, an electrical strength is created. These strengths, as before, have the form (2.12-2.17), where for $r > R$:

$$\mathbf{e}_z''(\mathbf{r}) + \mathbf{e}_z'(\mathbf{r}) \frac{1}{r} - \mathbf{e}_z(\mathbf{r}) \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{r^2} + \chi^2 \right) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{e}_\phi(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\alpha}{\chi} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{e}_z(\mathbf{r})}{r}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{e}_r(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{1}{\chi} \cdot \mathbf{e}_z'(\mathbf{r}), \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{e}_z(R) = \rho \cdot j_z(R), \quad (4)$$

where ρ is the specific resistance. The energy flux density reaching the part is determined by the formula (as follows from [3])

$$S_\phi = A \mathbf{e}_z(\mathbf{r}) \cdot h_r(\mathbf{r}), \quad (5)$$

where A is a constant.

4. Discussion

In [3] the solution of Maxwell's equations for a wire with direct current was found. The above conclusions from this solution are justified, at least, by the fact that they follow from Maxwell's equations.

The DC wire solution is easily transferred to the area outside the wire. Moreover, this solution is consistent with Oersted's experiment.

There is a refined BSL law, which is a consequence of Maxwell's equations. The refinements boil down to the fact that the vector of the magnetic strength created by the direct current is not directed strictly perpendicular to the direction of the current, but has three projections, with the magnitude of the circumferential projection prevailing.

It follows that the definition of the magnetic induction in the vicinity of the wire through the divergence of the vector potential is approximate, and the idea that the condition $\text{div}(A)=0$ naturally complements Maxwell's equations is incorrect.

The refined BSL law makes it possible to determine the energy flux directed from the wire to the magnetically sensitive element.

6. Epilogue

The vector potential A is introduced into the Maxwell equations by adding the last two lines:

$$\text{rot}(E) = -\mu \frac{\partial H}{\partial t}, \quad (\text{a})$$

$$\text{div}(E) = -\frac{\rho}{\epsilon}, \quad (\text{b})$$

$$\text{rot}(H) = J + \epsilon \frac{\partial E}{\partial t}, \quad (\text{c})$$

$$\text{div}(H) = 0, \quad (\text{d})$$

$$\text{rot}(A) = \mu H, \quad (\text{e})$$

$$\text{div}(A) = 0, \quad (\text{f})$$

where ρ is the electric charge density.

Let's remove the shining beauty of vector algebra from these equations and get 12 equations, which in Cartesian coordinates look like:

$$\frac{\partial E_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial z} = -\mu \frac{\partial H_x}{\partial t}, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial x} = -\mu \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial t}, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial y} = -\mu \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial t}, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial z} = -\frac{\rho}{\epsilon}, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial z} = J_x + \varepsilon \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial t}, \tag{5}$$

$$\frac{\partial H_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial x} = J_y + \varepsilon \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial t}, \tag{6}$$

$$\frac{\partial H_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial H_x}{\partial y} = J_z + \varepsilon \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial t}, \tag{7}$$

$$\frac{\partial H_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial z} = 0, \tag{8}$$

$$\frac{\partial A_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial A_y}{\partial z} = \mu H_x, \tag{9}$$

$$\frac{\partial A_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial A_z}{\partial x} = \mu H_y, \tag{10}$$

$$\frac{\partial A_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial A_x}{\partial y} = \mu H_z, \tag{11}$$

$$\frac{\partial A_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial A_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial A_z}{\partial z} = 0. \tag{12}$$

From (1-3) and (9-10) we find:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial A_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial A_y}{\partial z} \right) = \mu \frac{\partial H_x}{\partial t} = - \left(\frac{\partial E_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial z} \right), \tag{13}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial A_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial A_z}{\partial x} \right) = \mu \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial t} = - \left(\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial x} \right), \tag{14}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial A_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial A_x}{\partial y} \right) = \mu \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial t} = - \left(\frac{\partial E_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial y} \right). \tag{15}$$

In particular, from (13) we obtain:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial A_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial A_x}{\partial y} = - \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial y}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial A_y}{\partial x} &= - \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial x}, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial A_x}{\partial y} &= - \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial y} \end{aligned}$$

etc. In general, we write:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial A_a}{\partial b} = - \frac{\partial E_a}{\partial b}. \tag{16}$$

Conditions (16) are satisfied only if the solution of Maxwell's equations is a wave function. But the wave function cannot be an acceptable solution for physics, since it does not satisfy the law of conservation of energy [3]. So,

the existence of a vector potential contradicts the law of conservation of energy.

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